

DETERMINATION OF THE PLASTICITY INDEX USING SLOPE OF FALL CONE FLOW CURVE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents two simple equations that can be used to compute the plasticity index of soil using the correlation between the slope of the British fall cone flow curve and the plasticity index. The models were developed using British fall cone test results using soils of widely varying plasticity, including commercial bentonite.

INTRODUCTION

The plasticity index is the moisture content range at which the soil behaves as a plastic solid and is calculated as the arithmetic difference between liquid limit and plastic limit. The liquid limit can be determined using the percussion method [AASHTO T89-94] or the fall cone method [BS 1377: Part 2: 1990]. The liquid limit values obtained by the percussion and the fall cone methods are not the same. For soil with a low liquid limit, the fall cone method yields higher values of liquid limit than those obtained from the percussion method. For soil with a high liquid limit, the percussion method gives higher values of liquid limit than those obtained from the fall cone method. (Prakash and Sridharan 2006).

Determination of the plastic limit is highly operator-dependent and error-prone [Whyte 1982]. The procedure involves rolling an ellipsoidal soil thread to 3 mm until it crumbles [BS 1377, AASHTO T89]. The moisture content at which the ellipsoidal soil thread crumbles is taken as the plastic limit of the soil. Several researchers have attempted to improve the accuracy of thread-rolling devices [Bobrowski and Griekspoor (1992)]. Some have tried to assign the plastic limit with a specific value of the shear strength using the fall cone method [Campbell (1976), Wood and Wroth (1978), Harison (1988), Feng(2001), Sharma and Bora (2003), Maregesi (2022)]. Since the plasticity index computation involves using the operator-dependant test result of plastic limit, the accuracy of the plasticity index is affected. The plasticity index is one of the most critical indicator tests on which other engineering properties are correlated. Therefore, it is vital to

develop an improved method of determining the plasticity index of the soil rather than relying on the error-prone testing procedure of determining the plastic limit.

This paper presents two simple equations which can be used to compute the plasticity index of the soil using the slope of the British fall cone flow curve.

THE BRITISH FALL CONE LIQUID LIMIT FLOW CURVE

There are two common types of fall cones for determining the liquid limit in the world: the British cone and the Swedish cone. The British cone specifies 30° and 80g, and the penetration depth at the liquid limit is 20 mm, while the Swedish cone specifies 60°/60g, and a 10 mm penetration depth is the liquid limit. Essentially both types of cone yield approximately the same results [Farell (1997)].

The fall cone flow curve for liquid limit determination is modeled as linear within the penetration range of 20±5 mm [BS 1377- Part 2, (1990)]. Figure 1 shows an extended fall cone liquid limit flow curve for soil with a liquid limit of 19.7 and a plasticity index of 9. The fall cone flow curve was established using nine test runs with penetration values ranging from 3.3 mm to 23.5 mm. The fall cone flow curve was linearly modeled using a minimum of three test runs starting from the wet side and increasing one test run towards the dry side stepwise. It can be seen that the slope of the fall cone flow curve progressively decreased as the moisture content and penetration decreased, reaching a stable equilibrium value after including the 3.3 mm penetration and its corresponding moisture content. The fall cone flow curve's slope decreased from 4.643 within the penetration range of 25-15 mm to 2.883 when computed using penetration of 25 mm and 5 mm and its corresponding moisture content.

Figure 1(a): Variation of slope at diverse moisture and penetration values

Figure 1(b): Change in slope at diverse minimum penetration value

MODELS FOR COMPUTING PLASTICITY INDEX

Sixty soil samples, including commercial bentonite, were tested in the laboratory up to the lowest possible moisture content at which the soil penetration can be determined, i.e., within the penetration range of 3-5 mm. The moisture-penetration relationship was established using a linear regression model using the ordinary least square method for all soils within the 25-3 mm penetration range. After that, the slope of the fall cone flow curve for each soil was computed using penetration values of 25 mm and 5 mm and its corresponding moisture content, as shown in equation 1.

$$S = \frac{25 - 5}{w_{25} - w_5} = \frac{20}{w_{25} - w_5} \dots \dots (1)$$

where

w_{25} and w_5 is water content corresponding to 25 mm and 5 mm penetration value.

The flow index measures the rate at which the soil shear strength decreases with an increase in the soil moisture content. It is defined as the slope of the water content versus $\log_{10}(D)$ in the cone penetration method. Sridharan *et al.* [1999] reported the correlation between the fall cone flow index and the soil plasticity index and proposed to compute the plasticity index of the soil using equation 3 ($R^2=0.9801$). However, the data presented in their study indicates that for some soil samples, the flow index was computed using equation 2 using soils whose minimum fall cone penetration values were more than 10 mm. Calculating the slope of the fall cone flow curve using penetration values of more than 5 mm and its corresponding moisture content is precarious because the slope of the fall cone flow curve is yet to reach its equilibrium value (Figure 1).

$$I_{fc} = \frac{(W_1 - W_2)}{\log(D_1) - \log(D_2)} \dots \dots (2)$$

$$I_p = 0.75 I_{fc} \dots \dots (3)$$

Where

I_{fc} is the flow index, I_p is the plasticity index, W_1 and W_2 is the water content corresponding to penetration depth D_1 and D_2 , respectively, and I_p is the plasticity index.

The correlation between the fall cone flow index and the plasticity indices of the soil was also observed during this study. The flow index was computed using penetration values of 25 mm and 5 mm and its corresponding moisture contents using equation 4. The correlation between the fall cone flow index and the plasticity index can be modeled using the linear model ($R^2=0.9888$); however, the single-term power model fits the relationship better than the linear model ($R^2=0.9972$). The established power model is shown as equation 5, while the fitted moisture-penetration data is shown in Figure 2.

$$I_{fc} = \frac{W_{25} - W_5}{\log 25 - \log 5} \dots \dots (4)$$

Where

W_{25} and W_5 are the water content corresponding to 25 mm and 5 mm penetration, respectively.

$$I_p = 1.831(I_{fc} - 4.293)^{0.8191} \dots \dots (5)$$

Figure 2: the relationship between plasticity index and flow index

Figure 3: The relationship between the slope of the flow curve and the plasticity index of soil

Further analysis of the test results revealed that the plasticity index of the soil is highly correlated

with the slope of the flow curve plotted on linear scale ($R^2=0.9926$).

The correlation between the slope and the plasticity index of the soil is shown in Figure 3. Based on this correlation, the slope of the fall cone flow curve can be used to compute the plasticity index using equation 6 ($R^2=0.9926$)

$$I_p = 24.94(S + 0.03541)^{-1.044} \dots \dots (6)$$

Where

S is the slope of the flow curve computed using equation 1.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Figure 2 and 3 shows the correlation between the plasticity index, flow index, and slope of the flow curve. An excellent correlation does exist between the plasticity index and the slope and flow index of the fall cone flow curve, suggesting that equations 5 and 6 can be used to compute the plasticity index with reasonable accuracy. The comparison between the calculated plasticity index and the determined plasticity index is shown in Figure 4, from which it can be seen that the computed plasticity index closely agrees with the measured plasticity index for all two proposed models.

Figure 4: Comparison between measured and computed plasticity index

Figure 5 shows the residual analysis of both models, while Figure 6 shows the histogram and boxplot of the residual calculated using equation

5. It can be seen that the accuracy of the test results is very good, with 80% of the residual being within the range of $\pm 3\%$.

Figure 5: Differences between the computed and measured plasticity index (Residual plot)

Figure 6: Residual histogram and boxplot (Equation 5)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Two equations for computing the soil plasticity index using the slope of the fall cone liquid limit flow curve are proposed. The plasticity index computed using the proposed models is in close agreement with the determined value. The use of these proposed models for determining the plasticity index is cost and time-saving because both liquid and plasticity indexes can be determined from one test. The proposed models of computing the plasticity index using the slope

of the flow curve solve the problem of depending on the operator's judgment in the determination of soil plastic limit.

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